

ROBUST DESIGN OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH BUCKLING AND NATURAL FREQUENCIES CONSTRAINTS UNDER HYGROTHERMAL ENVIRONMENTS

Lu-Ping Chao and Bor-Han Wang
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Feng Chia University, Taichung, Taiwan, R.O.C.

ABSTRACT

A study of weight optimally designing fiber reinforced laminated composite plates subjected to constraints on buckling and natural frequencies under hygrothermal environments is presented. The formulation of the optimization design problem is accomplished by integrating design variables such as lamina thicknesses, fiber orientations, and fiber volume fractions. The first-order shear deformable theory is adopted herein due to deflections, rotations, and dimensional and constitutive changes due to moisture-induced swelling effects and temperature-induced expansions and contractions. Finite element modeling is then employed as numerical analysis for buckling behavior of laminated composite plate subjected to a variety of hygrothermal conditions under uniaxial compression for various boundary conditions.

INTRODUCTION

The extensive utilization of fiber reinforced polymeric composite materials in engineering practice has triggered focused attention on understanding the elastodynamic response characteristics of these materials in order that reliable design guidelines be distilled for engineering applications, since these advanced composite materials have the advantages, such as high strength, lightweight, corrosion resistance and low heat conduction, compared with the commercial metals. However, polymeric composite materials are relatively sensitive under severe hygrothermal environments compared with the commercial metals, it is imperative that the hygrothermoelastodynamic characteristics of these materials be carefully investigated and incorporated into design methodologies.

Over the last two decades significant progress has been made in the study of the buckling of laminated composite structures. Leissa [1] made a complete overview of consideration involved in the buckling of laminated composite plates. Raju et al. [2-4] developed finite element formulation to study the post-buckling behavior of a square plate resting on an elastic foundation subjected to biaxial compression and thermal loadings. Whitney and Ashton [5] employed a generalized form of Hooke's law to solve the buckling temperatures of thermal buckling problems for both symmetric and nonsymmetric laminated. Meyers and Hyer [6] used variational methods in

conjunction with a Raleigh-Ritz formulation to investigate the thermal buckling and postbuckling response of symmetrically laminated composite plates subjected to the condition of a uniform temperature change. Pandey and Sherbourne [7-8] cast the optimal thickness distribution for a rectangular, isotropic plate of given volume and plan dimensions in order to maximize the uniaxial buckling load. Shin et al. [9] took the thickness of the layers as the design variables to find out the maximum buckling loading of symmetric laminated plates by using the finite element method.

The increasing recommendation of employing fiber-reinforced composite materials in the design of structures subjected to buckling loads will further exacerbate the demand for considering thermal and hygroscopic effects. The reason for this is that fiber-reinforced laminated composite structures are usually subjected to changing environmental conditions during both initial manufacture and final application. The polymeric matrix materials of laminated composite structures are much more susceptible to hygrothermal deformation than the fiber and some high performance fibers have small, or even negative, coefficients of thermal expansion, the hygrothermal effect of the laminated composite plates is therefore much higher in the transverse direction than in the longitudinal direction. The objective of this paper is to develop a design methodology to study the weight optimal design of fiber reinforced laminated composite plates subjected to constraints on buckling and natural frequency under hygrothermal environments. The first-order shear deformation plate theory is adopted herein due to deflections, rotations, and dimensional and constitutive changes due to moisture-induced swelling effects and temperature-induced expansions and contractions. Finite element modeling is then employed as numerical analysis for buckling behavior of laminated composite plate subjected to a variety of hygrothermal conditions under uniaxial compression for various boundary conditions. The successive quadratic programming method is adopted for optimal algorithm.

THEORETICAL MODELS OF POLYMERIC LAMINATED PLATES

In order to establish a variable theoretical model for analyzing the buckling behavior of laminated composite plates under hygrothermal environments, a micromechanical model of a laminae and the macromechanical model of a laminate must be established. The elastic moduli of fibrous composite materials are first expressed as a function of the properties of the constituents, which are the fiber and matrix properties, and also the fiber volume fraction. Then, in terms of micromechanical model of a lamina, Shapery [10] derived expressions for the longitudinal and transverse coefficients of thermal expansion of a composite with isotropic fibers embedded in an isotropic matrix based on energy considerations. These expressions may be written as

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{E_f \alpha_f V_f + E_m \alpha_m V_m}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} \quad , \quad \alpha_2 = (1 + \nu_m) \alpha_m V_m + (1 + \nu_f) \alpha_f V_f - \alpha_1 \nu_{12} \quad (1)$$

On the other hand, Tsai [11] obtained expressions for the longitudinal and transverse coefficients of hygroscopic expansion of a lamina. These expressions may be written as

$$\beta_1 = \frac{S E_m}{S_m E_1} \beta_m \quad , \quad \beta_2 = \frac{S}{S_m} (1 + \nu_m) \beta_m - \nu_{12} \beta_1 \quad (2)$$

where S and S_m are the specific gravity of lamina and matrix. The stress-strain constitutive equations for the k th lamina of arbitrary orientation can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix}^k = [T]^{-1} [Q] [T]^{-T} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x - \alpha_x \Delta T - \beta_x \Delta M \\ \varepsilon_y - \alpha_y \Delta T - \beta_y \Delta M \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{xy} - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{xy} \Delta T - \frac{1}{2} \beta_{xy} \Delta M \end{Bmatrix}^k \quad (3)$$

In terms of macromechanical model of a laminate, the first-order shear deformation plate theory is adopted to analysis buckling behavior under hygrothermal effects. To account for the deflection of the composite plate, the nonlinear strain - displacement relationship is considered herein and von Karman strain is employed. The strain field then obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_x &= \frac{\partial U_o}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial W_o}{\partial x} \right)^2 + z \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial x} = \varepsilon_1^0 + z \kappa_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 = \varepsilon_y &= \frac{\partial V_o}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial W_o}{\partial y} \right)^2 + z \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial y} = \varepsilon_2^0 + z \kappa_2 \\ \varepsilon_4 = \gamma_{yz} &= \frac{\partial W_o}{\partial y} + \psi_y \quad \varepsilon_5 = \gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial W_o}{\partial x} + \psi_x \\ \varepsilon_6 = \gamma_{xy} &= \frac{\partial U_o}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial V_o}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial W_o}{\partial x} \frac{\partial W_o}{\partial y} + z \left(\frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial x} \right) = \varepsilon_6^0 + z \kappa_6 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Combining Equation (3) with Equation (4) and integrating lamina-by-lamina over the thickness of a laminate plate, one obtains the following relations of stress resultants in matrix form as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \{N\} \\ \{M\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A] & [B] \\ [B] & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\varepsilon^o\} \\ \{K\} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \{\hat{Q}\} = \begin{bmatrix} - \\ A \end{bmatrix} \{\hat{\varepsilon}\} \quad (5)$$

FORMULATIONS OF BUCKLING BEHAVIOR AND NATURE FREQUENCY

Finite element method is employed herein for numerical analysis of nonlinear buckling behavior of laminated composite plates subjected to a variety of hygrothermal conditions. The isoparametric quadrilateral element, which has eight nodes and every node has five degrees, was selected to calculate buckling problem and natural frequencies of laminated composite plates. Assume a rectangular laminated composite plate is subjected to transverse loading $q(x, y)$ and in-plane edge external loading N_x and N_y . Internal strain energy U of composite plate can be determined by integrating the products of strains and stress results over the volume, this is

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h_2}^{h_2} \int_0^b \int_0^a (\sigma_x \varepsilon_x + \sigma_y \varepsilon_y + \sigma_{yz} \varepsilon_{yz} + \sigma_{xz} \varepsilon_{xz} + \sigma_{xy} \varepsilon_{xy}) dx dy dz \quad (6)$$

The works done by external loadings q , N_x , N_y and the total potential energy are given by

$$V_1 = \int_0^b \int_0^a q(x, y) w dx dy, \quad V_2 = \int_0^b [N_x u]_{x=0}^{x=a} dy + \int_0^a [N_y v]_{y=0}^{y=b} dx, \quad \Pi = U - V_1 - V_2 \quad (7)$$

Based on principle of minimum total potential energy $\delta \Pi = 0$ and finite element modeling, the governing equation form can be obtained as

$$([K] + [K_N])\{d\} = \{F\} \quad (8)$$

where $[K]$ is the global linear stiffness matrix, $[K_N]$ is the global nonlinear stiffness matrix, $\{d\}$ is a column vector containing the nodal displacements, and $\{F\}$ is a column vector containing the nodal external loadings. If the composite laminated plate is subjected to lateral external loadings under hygrothermal environments, that is $q(x, y) = 0$, the standard eigenvalue problem which is physically the critical nonlinear buckling problem is therefore obtained as

$$([K] + [K_N] + \lambda[K_g])\{d\} = \{0\} \quad (9)$$

where $[K_g]$ is the global geometry stiffness matrix or initial stress matrix. In this paper, the nonlinear buckling problem of laminated composite plate under hygrothermal environments is considered. Solving Equation (9), Newton-Raphson iteration method was employed to obtain the approximate solutions of deflections and in-plane stress resultant. The eigenvalue λ is determined by Jacobi's method and buckling stress is the product of eigenvalue and in-plane stress resultant. For the laminated composite plates, the natural frequencies and the associated natural modes are obtained by the following governing equation :

$$[K]\{\phi_i\} = \omega_i^2[M]\{\phi_i\} \quad (10)$$

where $[K]$ is still the global linear stiffness matrix, ω_i is the i th natural frequency and ϕ_i is the associated the i th natural mode of the i th natural frequency. $[M]$ is the global mass matrix of a laminated composite plate, which are called consistent mass matrix, through using the same shape functions as used in the stiffness matrix.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF OPTIMAL DESIGN

Since the laminated composite plate will be selected as a symmetric structure, the half of the total number n of lamina are considered in the design process. Therefore, every k th lamina has three design variables, that is, the thickness h_k , the fiber orientation θ_k , and the fiber volume fraction V_{fk} . The total weight W of a laminated composite plate with n lamina will be chosen as objective function. The design variables, objective function, and corresponding constraints present as follows :

$$W(\underline{X}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \rho_i \times h_i \times A, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

$$\underline{X} = \{h_k, \theta_k, V_{fk}\}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2}$$

$$\text{Buckling constraint : } (N_{cr})_{op} \geq (N_{cr})_{in}$$

$$\text{Natural frequency constraint : } (f_1)_{op} \geq (f_1)_{in}$$

$$\text{Transverse displacement in the middle of the plate constraint : } (u)_{op} \leq (u)_{in}$$

where ρ_i and h_i are the density and thickness of the i -th lamina, A , the geometrically area of the laminated composite plate, the subscript (op) represents the optimal design requirement, (in) denotes the lower or upper bound constraints, N_{cr} , the first mode buckling loading of the

laminated composite plate, f_1 , is the first mode natural frequency, u , the out-of-plane displacement of the laminated composite plate in the mid-point. Therefore, the optimization design problem can be mathematically written in the following form including objective function, explicit constraints and implicit constraints.

Find design variables \tilde{X} such that minimizes the objective function $F(\tilde{X}) = W(\tilde{X})$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{subject to the constraints } & (N_{cr})_{op} - (N_{cr})_{in} \geq 0 & h_{\min} \leq h_k \leq h_{\max} \\ & (f_1)_{op} - (f_1)_{in} \geq 0 & \theta_{\min} \leq \theta_k \leq \theta_{\max} \\ & (u)_{op} - (u)_{in} \leq 0 & V_{f \min} \leq V_{fk} \leq V_{f \max} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The task of designing a square plate with optimal requirement, which is to be fabricated from a symmetric fibrous composite laminate, is demonstrated herein as the application of the proposed methodology. The fibrous composite material utilized to analysis and optimal design of composite plates under hygrothermal effects was graphite fiber T300 [12] and epoxy [13], and their parameters of material properties are

$$\begin{aligned} E_f = 230 \text{ GPa} \quad E_{fy} = 15.2 \text{ GPa} \quad G_{fy} = 9 \text{ GPa} \quad E_m = (3.51 - 0.003T - 0.142M) \text{ GPa} \quad \nu_f = 0.203 \quad \nu_m = 0.34 \\ \alpha_f = -0.54 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C \quad \alpha_m = 45 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C \quad T : ^\circ C \quad M : \text{wt \% } H_2O \quad \beta_m = 2.68 \times 10^{-3} / \text{wt \% } H_2O \end{aligned}$$

The effects of fiber orientation on buckling load with simply (SSSS), simply-hinge (SHSH), and simply-fixed (SFSF) supports in the four edges for a stack lay-up $[\theta / -\theta]_4$ laminated composite square plate under room temperature are shown in Figure 1. The length of each edge (a) equals 25.4 cm and the ratio of edge length with thickness (a/h) is 20. From Figure 1, the maximum of critical buckling capacity (N_{cr}) which the laminated plate can be subjected is happened in $\theta = 45^\circ$ with simply supported edges, since the corresponding transverse displacement in the middle of laminated plate is minimum as shown in Figure 2 and it implies the total stiffness is biggest. Compared with the three different kinds of edge supported from Figure 1, the laminated composite plate with simply supported edges will have best capability to subject to buckling failure. The hygroscopic effects on buckling load with SSSS boundary condition and fiber volume fraction $V_f = 0.5$ for a stack lay-up $[-\theta / \theta / -\theta / \theta]_s$ composite square plate are shown in Figure 3, where N_{cr}° is the buckling load without moisture content. Figure 4 presents the hygrothermal effects on critical buckling value with simply support edges for a stack lay-up $[-45^\circ / 45^\circ / -45^\circ / 45^\circ]_s$ composite plate, $a/h=30$, and $V_f=0.5$.

For the weight optimization design of a simply supported square symmetric laminated composite plate with buckling capability, natural frequency, and transverse displacement as the constraints, the total number of lamina is 8 and four plies are considered in the design process to demonstrate the proposed methodology. Therefore, every k th has three design variables h_k, θ_k, V_{fk} , where k is 1,2,3,4. The constraints $(N_{cr})_{in}, (f_1)_{in}$, and $(u)_{in}$ in Equation (11) are chosen as 3000 kN/m, 850 Hz, and 1.2 cm, respectively. The upper and lower bound of the design variables h_k, θ_k, V_{fk} in Equation (11) are $h_{\min} = 0.7 \text{ mm}$, $h_{\max} = 2.0 \text{ mm}$, $\theta_{\min} = -90^\circ$, $\theta_{\max} = 90^\circ$, $V_{f \min} = 0.4$, and $V_{f \max} = 0.7$.

The objective function and corresponding constraints presented in Equation (11) are optimized by using the successive quadratic programming method. The results of a square symmetric laminated composite plate, which has 25.4cm in the length of each edge, are given in Table 1 for hydrothermal conditions in $T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $M=0\%$ and Table 2 in $T=95^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $M=8\%$. The reason to choose the moisture content, $M=8\%$, is that the moisture concentration in most epoxies can be as high as 8% [11]. It should be noted that Equation (11) defines a class of nonconvex programming problems in the optimal design of composite laminates, consequently, the optimal solution will only converge to a local minimum. From Table 1 and Table 2, it can be observed that the total weight of the laminated composite plate in the severe hydrothermal environments ($T=95^{\circ}\text{C}$, $M=8\%$) is bigger than the weight in the room temperature ($T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$, $M=0\%$), since laminated plate needs to increase its total thickness and/or fiber volume fraction to compensate the loss of the total stiffness owing to hydrothermal effects.

CONCLUSIONS

A methodology of weight optimal design for fibrous laminated composite plates incorporating nonlinear buckling, natural frequency, and transverse displacement as constraints under hydrothermal environments has been presented. The formulation of the optimization design problem is accomplished by integrating design variables such as lamina thicknesses, fiber orientations, and fiber volume fractions. The effects of boundary conditions, fiber orientations, and hydrothermal effects on the nonlinear buckling capacities for square laminated composite plates are investigated. An illustrative example involving weight optimal design of a square plate with nonlinear buckling capacity, natural frequency and transverse displacement as constraints demonstrates the significance of incorporating hydrothermal effects into design consideration for fibrous laminated composite structures where severe variations in the moisture and temperature conditions may be encountered.

REFERENCES

1. A. W. Leissa, A review of laminated composite plate buckling. *Appl. Mech. Rev.* **40**, No. 5, 575-591(1987).
2. K. K. Raju and G. V. Rao, Thermal post-buckling of a square plate resting on an elastic foundation by finite element method. *Computers and Structures* **28**, No. 2, 195-199(1980).
3. N. R. Naidu, K. K. Raju and G. V. Rao, Post-buckling of a square plate resting on an elastic foundation under biaxial compression. *Computers and Structures* **37**, No. 3, 343-345(1990).
4. K. K. Raju and G. V. Rao, Post-buckling of point supported square plate resting on elastic foundation subject to thermal or mechanical loading. *Computers and Structures* **40**, No. 4, 1061-1064(1991).
5. J. M. Whitney and J. E. Ashton, Effect of environment on the elastic response of layered composite plates. *AIAA Journal* **9**, No. 9, (1971).
6. C. A. Meyers and M. W. Hyer, Thermal buckling and postbuckling of symmetrically laminated composite plates. *Journal of Thermal Stresses*, 519-540(1991).
7. M. D. Pandey and A. N. Sherbourne, Mechanics of shape optimization in plate buckling. *Journal of Engineering Mechanics* **118**, No. 6, 1249-1266(1992).
8. M. D. Pandey and A. N. Sherbourne, Some anomalies of shape optimization in plate buckling. *Mechanics Research Communications* **19**, 37-43(1992).
9. Y. S. Shin, R. T. Haftka, L. T. Watson and R. H. Plaut, Design of laminated plates for maximum buckling load. *Journal of Composite Materials* **23**, 348-368(1989).
10. R. A. Shapery, Thermal expansion coefficients of composite materials based on energy principles. *Journal of Composite Materials* **2**, 380-404(1968).
11. S. W. Tsai, Introduction to composite materials. Technomic Publishing Co. (1980).

12. D. E. Bowles and S. S. Tompkins, Prediction of Coefficients of Thermal Expansion for Unidirectional Composites. *Journal of Composite Materials* 23, 370-381(1989).
13. D. F. Adams and A. K. Miller, Hygrothermal microstresses in a unidirectional composite exhibiting inelastic materials behavior. *Journal of Composite Materials* 11, 285-299(1977).

Table 1. The optimization design results of a square plate under hygrothermal environments in room temperature and without moisture contents.

Quantity		case 1		case 2	
		Initial	Optimal	Initial	Optimal
lamina thickness	h_1	1.60 mm	0.89 mm	1.15 mm	0.89 mm
	h_2	1.60 mm	1.77 mm	1.15 mm	1.56 mm
	h_3	1.60 mm	0.89 mm	1.15 mm	0.89 mm
	h_4	1.60 mm	0.95 mm	1.15 mm	1.15 mm
fiber orientation	θ_1	30.0°	-45.0°	70.0°	-45.0°
	θ_2	30.0°	45.0°	70.0°	45.0°
	θ_3	30.0°	-45.0°	70.0°	-45.0°
	θ_4	30.0°	45.0°	70.0°	45.0°
fiber volume fraction	V_{f1}	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7
	V_{f2}	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7
	V_{f3}	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7
	V_{f4}	0.6	0.58	0.7	0.68
total weight w		1.365kg	0.9718kg	0.9875kg	0.9691kg

Table 2. The optimization design results of a square plate under hygrothermal environments in room T=95°C and M=8%.

Quantity		case 1		case 2	
		Initial	Optimal	Initial	Optimal
lamina thickness	h_1	1.60 mm	0.89 mm	1.05 mm	0.89 mm
	h_2	1.60 mm	1.65 mm	1.05 mm	1.52 mm
	h_3	1.60 mm	1.05 mm	1.05 mm	1.14 mm
	h_4	1.60 mm	1.12 mm	1.05 mm	1.16 mm
fiber orientation	θ_1	-20.0°	-45.0°	-30.0°	-45.0°
	θ_2	20.0°	45.0°	30.0°	44.0°
	θ_3	-20.0°	-45.0°	-30.0°	-44.0°
	θ_4	20.0°	45.0°	30.0°	45.0°
fiber volume fraction	V_{f1}	0.58	0.7	0.65	0.7
	V_{f2}	0.58	0.7	0.65	0.7
	V_{f3}	0.58	0.7	0.65	0.7
	V_{f4}	0.58	0.7	0.65	0.7
total weight w		1.3166kg	1.0203kg	0.9052kg	1.0204kg

Figure 1. The comparison of critical buckling capacities for simply, simply-hinge, and simply-fixed supports.

Figure 2. Transverse displacement in the middle of laminated plate versus fiber orientation.

Figure 3. The comparison of critical buckling capacities for various moisture contents with simply supported edges.

Figure 4. Hydrothermal effects on critical buckling capacities with simply supported edges.